

Interchannel Mismatch Calibration Techniques for Time-Interleaved SAR ADCs

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Abstract—Interleaving is a powerful technique that boosts the speed of an ADC. The power efficiency of such a technique is mainly affected by the overhead of the circuitry used to mitigate the impact of inter-channel mismatches on the ADC’s performance. This paper reviews some of the most important methods of calibrating such mismatches and presents a frequency-domain analysis of timing skew in a TI ADC. A new calibration approach is also proposed that calibrates the timing and offset mismatches between the channels simultaneously. Behavioral modeling simulations of a 15-channel 10-b 2GS/s TI SAR ADC show an improvement of 35 dB in the SFDR after calibration. The impact of circuit nonidealities and noise is also assessed, and mitigation techniques are proposed.

Index Terms—SAR analog-to-digital converter (ADC), time-interleaved ADC, timing-skew calibration

I. INTRODUCTION

Time interleaving is a technique that allows multiple identical analog-to-digital converters (ADCs) to operate in parallel and process the input at a faster rate than the operating speed of each individual converter. If M channels¹ operate in parallel, then the overall ADC’s speed increases by a factor M compared to the speed of a single sub-ADC. As such, the maximum *realistic* speed of the sub-ADCs is a limiting factor to the maximum achievable speed of the time-interleaved (TI) ADC. Another limiting factor is the speed of the input sampler. It was proven in [1] that, if the sampler is the speed bottleneck, interleaving beyond $0.44(N + 1)$ offers little improvement.

Time-interleaving can be exploited to improve the power efficiency under certain conditions. The Walden figure-of-merit (FoM_W), which is defined as

$$FoM_W = \frac{P}{2^{ENOB} \cdot f_s}, \quad (1)$$

where P is the power consumption, ENOB is the effective number of bits and f_s is the Nyquist-rate sampling frequency, is typically used to report on the energy efficiency of an ADC. As long as the power consumption of a sub-ADC scales linearly with the sampling speed, the equivalent time-interleaved ADC will always be less energy-efficient than its constituent sub-ADCs because of the overhead associated with interleaving, e.g. the multi-phase clock generation and

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¹Throughout this article, M , N , f_s , T_s and f_{in} denote the number of channels (sub-ADCs) of the TI ADC, the resolution, the sampling frequency, the sampling period and the maximum input frequency, respectively.

Fig. 1. ADC output spectrum (a) before and (b) after applying chopping.

distribution and the correction of interchannel mismatches [1]. However, as the conversion speed of a sub-ADC approaches the limits (“performance knee”) of the technology, the power-speed trade-off becomes nonlinear and the interleaving may keep the power-efficiency from excessive degradation.

Sections II and IV review a number of the most effective techniques for detecting/correcting inter-channel mismatches (gain, offset and timing mismatch) in a TI ADC. Section III discusses a frequency-domain method to derive a closed-form formula that quantifies the SNR degradation of a TI ADC due to the timing mismatch. Details of the proposed mismatch calibration method along with practical nonidealities are presented in Sections V and VI-A. The simulation results are given in Section VII.

II. OFFSET AND GAIN MISMATCH CALIBRATION

The approach used to estimate the offset mismatch error assumes that the *mean value* of the output of each sub-ADC corresponds to its offset error [2]. To achieve this, the mean value of a batch of k samples from each sub-ADC is calculated (i.e. accumulation and division by k) and the result is subtracted from the output in the end. In extreme cases, e.g. when the input is a sine wave, the offset may not be distinguished from the input signal, in which case, a randomization can be employed [2].

The idea for estimating the gain mismatch error is that the *variance* of the output of each sub-ADC corresponds to its gain error [3], [4]. To reduce the power dissipation, a down-sampling can also be applied. Ref. [5] proposed a frequency-domain approach to cancel the gain mismatch in a ($M=2$)-channel TI ADC. This approach is based on the fact that gain mismatch between the channels in a TI ADC causes spurs (images) in the ADC output spectrum at frequencies of

$$f_g = \pm f_{in} + k \cdot \frac{f_s}{M}, \quad (2)$$

where k is an integer. Specifically, for a single input tone at f_0 , the gain mismatch causes an image at a certain frequency, say f_i . By applying a *chopping* at the ADC output, one could swap the frequencies at which the main input signal and the gain-mismatch induced image signal occur. This would cause the image to move to f_0 and the input to move to f_i , as shown in Fig. 1. In the end, multiplying the original ADC output and the chopped output would result in a dc component that

Fig. 2. Gain mismatch detection using a frequency-domain method.

is proportional to the amount of the gain mismatch. A block diagram implementation of such a technique is shown in Fig. 2. In this figure, y_1 and y_2 are the ADC outputs of channel one and two, respectively. This idea can also be easily used for $M > 2$, where one channel can be taken as a reference and then this gain mismatch detection approach is applied to all other channels one by one.

III. THE EFFECT OF TIMING MISMATCH

The effect of timing mismatch was discussed in [1] for a 2-channel TI ADC using a frequency-domain analysis. Here, we follow the same methodology to work out the effects of timing error for a more general case of a *multi*-channel TI ADC as follows. For an input signal $x(t)$ with a bandwidth of f_{in} , the output of an M -channel time-interleaved ADC globally sampled at f_s can be expressed as

$$y(t) = \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} x\left(kT + \frac{T}{M}i\right) \cdot \delta\left(t - kT - \frac{T}{M}i\right), \quad (3)$$

where $T = M/f_s$ is the sampling period of each channel. This means, for a Nyquist-rate ADC, $T \leq M/(2f_{in})$. In the frequency domain, (3) becomes

$$Y(f) = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{i=1}^M X(f) * \left[\sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \delta\left(f - \frac{k}{T}\right) e^{-j2\pi \frac{k}{M}i} \right]. \quad (4)$$

Specifically, the output of channel i is

$$Y_i(f) = \frac{1}{T} X(f) * \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \delta\left(f - \frac{k}{T}\right) e^{-j2\pi \frac{k}{M}i}, \quad (5)$$

the magnitude of which comprises copies of $X(f)$ with a frequency shift of $1/T = f_s/M = 2f_{in}/M$. The aliasing between the copies is canceled out by the re-interleaving multiplexer at the output, provided there is no timing mismatch between the channels.

An error delay, ΔT_i , in the sampling moment of a specific channel i is equivalent to assuming that the input signal of the channel is delayed by that amount [i.e. $x_i(t) = x(t + \Delta T_i)$]. Assuming that ΔT_i is small (relative to T), then $x(t + \Delta T_i) \approx x(t) + \Delta T_i dx/dt$. This means a (persistent) timing mismatch creates a magnitude error equal to $\Delta T_i dx/dt$ in the time domain, and $j2\pi f \Delta T_i X(f)$ in the frequency domain. Eq. (5) can thus be adjusted as

$$Y_i(f) = \frac{1}{T} [X(f) + j2\pi f \Delta T_i X(f)] * \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \delta\left(f - \frac{k}{T}\right) e^{-j2\pi \frac{k}{M}i}. \quad (6)$$

Fig. 3. Illustration of the timing mismatch error of one single channel as presented in (10) for a random input signal with flat power spectral density.

The error term in (6) can be extracted as

$$E_i(f) = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} j2\pi\left(f - \frac{k}{T}\right) \Delta T_i X\left(f - \frac{k}{T}\right) e^{-j2\pi \frac{k}{M}i}. \quad (7)$$

By considering the frequency span of (7) from $-f_{in}$ to $+f_{in}$, the ‘noise’ power due to the timing mismatch for the i -th channel can be found as

$$P_{n,i} = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-f_{in}}^{+f_{in}} \left[2\pi\left(f - \frac{k}{T}\right) \Delta T_i\right]^2 S_X\left(f - \frac{k}{T}\right) df, \quad (8)$$

where $S_X(f)$ is the power spectral density of the input signal. Given that the input signal is band-limited within $\pm f_{in}$, and that $1/T \geq 2f_{in}/M$ to satisfy the Nyquist condition, the term $S_X(f - k/T)$ in (8) can be excluded from the integration for $k \geq M$ and $k \leq -M$. Thus, (8) becomes

$$P_{n,i} = \sum_{k=-(M-1)}^{M-1} \int_{-f_{in}}^{+f_{in}} [2\pi\left(f - \frac{k}{T}\right) \Delta T_i]^2 S_X\left(f - \frac{k}{T}\right) df \quad (9)$$

$$= \int_{-f_{in}}^{+f_{in}} (2\pi f \Delta T_i)^2 S_X(f) df + 2 \sum_{k=1}^{M-1} \int_{-f_{in}}^{+f_{in}} [2\pi\left(f - \frac{k}{T}\right) \Delta T_i]^2 S_X\left(f - \frac{k}{T}\right) df. \quad (10)$$

For the sake of illustration, let us now assume that $S_X(f)$ is flat within $\pm f_{in}$ and equal to $\eta/2$. The terms in (10) would then look like what is shown in Fig. 3, where the shaded area is the area for integration. In order to compute the k -th integral in (10), we can write it as

$$P_{n,i}^k = \int_{-f_{in}}^{+f_{in}} [2\pi\left(f - \frac{k}{T}\right) \Delta T_i]^2 S_X\left(f - \frac{k}{T}\right) df \quad (11)$$

$$= \frac{\eta}{2} \int_{-f_{in}+k/T}^{+f_{in}} [2\pi\left(f - \frac{k}{T}\right) \Delta T_i]^2 df. \quad (12)$$

Substituting $1/T$ by $2f_{in}/M$ in (12) and working out the integral results in

$$P_{n,i}^k = \frac{4}{3} \pi^2 \eta \Delta T_i^2 f_{in}^3 \left[1 - \frac{3k}{M} + \frac{6k^2}{M^2} - \frac{4k^3}{M^3}\right]. \quad (13)$$

Therefore,

$$P_{n,i} = P_{n,i}(0) + 2 \sum_{k=1}^{M-1} P_{n,i}(k) \quad (14)$$

$$= \frac{4}{3} \pi^2 \eta \Delta T_i^2 f_{in}^3 \left[1 + 2 \sum_{k=1}^{M-1} \left(1 - \frac{3k}{M} + \frac{6k^2}{M^2} - \frac{4k^3}{M^3} \right) \right] \quad (15)$$

$$= \frac{4}{3} M \pi^2 \eta \Delta T_i^2 f_{in}^3. \quad (16)$$

And, finally, the total timing mismatch ‘noise’ power for all the channels is

$$P_n = \sum_{i=1}^{M-1} P_{n,i} = \frac{4}{3} M \pi^2 \eta \left(\sum_{i=1}^{M-1} \Delta T_i^2 \right) f_{in}^3. \quad (17)$$

The signal power is also equal to

$$P_{sig} = M^2 \int_{-f_{in}}^{+f_{in}} \frac{\eta}{2} = M^2 \eta f_{in}. \quad (18)$$

From (17) and (18), the signal-to-noise ratio due to the timing mismatch ($\text{SNR}_{\Delta T}$) can be computed as

$$\text{SNR}_{\Delta T} = \frac{3M}{4\pi^2 \left(\sum_{i=1}^{M-1} \Delta T_i^2 \right) f_{in}^2}. \quad (19)$$

The term $\sum_{i=1}^{M-1} \Delta T_i^2$ in (19) is worth noting. It is known that the sum of squares of k independent standard normal random variables exhibits a so-called ‘chi-squared’ distribution, $\chi^2(k)$, with k degrees of freedom. Now, assuming that the timing errors ΔT_i are independent random variables with a Gaussian distribution of zero mean and standard deviation $\sigma_{\Delta T}$ (i.e. $\Delta T_i = \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\Delta T}^2)$), then the term $\sum_{i=1}^{M-1} \Delta T_i^2$ is a random variable with a distribution of

$$\sum_{i=1}^{M-1} \Delta T_i^2 \sim \sigma_{\Delta T}^2 \cdot \chi^2(M-1). \quad (20)$$

It is now possible to replace the term $\sum_{i=1}^{M-1} \Delta T_i^2$ in (19) with its expected value, which is equal to k in the case of a chi-squared random variable with k degrees of freedom, that is

$$\mathbf{E} \left[\sum_{i=1}^{M-1} \Delta T_i^2 \right] = (M-1) \cdot \sigma_{\Delta T}^2. \quad (21)$$

By substituting (21) into (19), we have

$$\text{SNR}_{\Delta T} = \frac{M}{M-1} \cdot \frac{3}{4\pi^2 \sigma_{\Delta T}^2 f_{in}^2}. \quad (22)$$

In the end, to compute the SNR degradation due to the timing mismatch in an N -bit ADC, the quantization noise should also be taken into account. The signal-to-noise ratio due to an N -bit quantization (SNR_Q) can be approximated by the expression

$$\text{SNR}_Q = 3 \cdot 2^{2N-1}. \quad (23)$$

By merging (22) and (23), we can find the total SNR as

$$\text{SNR}_{\text{tot}} = \left(\frac{1}{\text{SNR}_Q} + \frac{1}{\text{SNR}_{\Delta T}} \right)^{-1} \quad (24)$$

$$= \left(\frac{1}{3 \times 2^{2N-1}} + \frac{4(M-1)}{3M} \pi^2 f_{in}^2 \sigma_{\Delta T}^2 \right)^{-1}. \quad (25)$$

Fig. 4. Block diagram and waveforms of the clocks for the hypothetical sampling solution using a master switch.

Using (25) and for a 12-bit 16-channel TI ADC with an input frequency of $f_{in} = 3.2$ GHz (outlined as the ‘case-study’ hereafter²), a constraint of an SNR degradation lower than 1.5 dB imposes

$$\sigma_{\Delta T} < 11.5 \text{ fs}. \quad (26)$$

Monte-Carlo simulations in MATLAB showed such a timing error resulted in an average SNDR degradation of 1.65 dB, which is in good accordance with the theoretical value of 1.5 dB. Note that this ADC is intended for Nyquist-rate applications; however, in case of input signals in the second or higher Nyquist zones, and as for any other calibration technique reported to date, the requirement set by (26) would be more strict. For instance, if $f_{in} = f_s$ for our case-study ADC, the requirement of (26) becomes $\sigma_{\Delta T} < 5.5$ fs.

One method to deal with the timing skew error is to employ a *master* sampler that is followed by the sampling switches of the sub-ADCs [7]–[10], as shown in Fig. 4. The master sampling switch S_M samples the input voltage on the capacitor C_M , as shown in the figure, at a sampling rate of f_s and is driven by the master clock CLK_S . If the sampling switches of the sub-ADCs sample while the voltage on C_M is stationary (i.e. when S_M is open), then any timing skew in the clocks of the sub-ADCs would not cause any harm. However, this simple method comes with major drawbacks. First, the available sampling acquisition time for the master switch S_M is half that of the sub-ADC sampling switches in a conventional TI ADC, which makes the design of this master switch challenging, especially for a high resolution N . Second, and more importantly, upon the closing of the sub-ADC sampling switches, charge sharing occurs between C_M and C_{S_i} , where C_{S_i} is the sampling capacitance of the i -th sub-ADC (which in the case of a SAR ADC, is approximately the DAC capacitance C_{DAC}). This charge sharing causes an attenuation of the input signal and a loss of the dynamic range of the ADC by almost a factor $\alpha = C_{\text{DAC}} / (C_{\text{DAC}} + C_M)$. Making α much smaller than one implies $C_{\text{DAC}} \ll C_M$. This calls for either a very small C_{DAC} or a very large C_M . Due to the kT/C noise and random mismatch limitations, a small C_{DAC} does not easily lend itself to a high-resolution ADC. A large C_M also makes the design of the master switch very challenging for high speed and/or high resolution, and it increases power dissipation. To avoid this undesired charge sharing, one might add a buffer between the master sampler and the samplers of interleaved channels. However, this buffer needs to be able to operate at the sampling frequency of the ADC f_s , which would demand a huge power consumption for

²These specifications are identical to the ones for the ADC reported in [6], since we aim to make a comparison later.

Fig. 5. Block diagram of a timing skew calibration technique using a pilot tone as the input.

the typical frequency ranges ($> \text{GHz}$) where a time-interleaved architecture is required.

Another way of dealing with the timing error in TI ADCs is through calibration, which is discussed in detail in the subsequent section.

IV. TIMING MISMATCH CALIBRATION TECHNIQUES

The timing mismatch calibration in interleaved ADCs is performed in two phases: detection and correction. In the following, the various methods for timing error detection and correction that have been proposed in the literature are discussed.

A. Detection

1) *Foreground*: Foreground calibration of the timing mismatch is performed upon the start-up of the chip and before the actual ADC conversion kicks off. One way is to apply a specific known input to the ADC through which the timing errors can be computed. In [11], a *linear ramp* signal was proposed for this purpose. Ideally, if there were no timing errors, the sampling instances of the sub-ADCs would sample the input linear ramp at equidistant intervals, which would result in equally spaced ADC output codes. A timing skew at any of the sampling instances would cause these output codes to deviate from their ideal value. The timing error for channel i would then be equal to

$$\Delta T_i = \frac{\Delta D_i}{m}, \quad (27)$$

where ΔD_i is the difference between the ideal output of the i -th sub-ADC and ‘skewed’ one, while m is the slope of the input ramp. In order to have accuracy of at least 1 LSB, the minimum slope of the ramp signal has to be [11]

$$m_{\min} = \frac{\text{LSB}}{\Delta T}, \quad (28)$$

meaning that, in face of a maximum clock timing skew ΔT , the ramp should be steep enough such that the ADC output deviates of at least 1 LSB from its nominal value. However, it can be shown that such a minimum slope results in an input frequency that exceeds the ADC Nyquist frequency, i.e. $f_s/2$. In [6], [12], instead of a ramp, a sinusoidal input of frequency f_s was used. Although generating a sine wave is easier than the ramp, the problem of limited input bandwidth of the ADC still persists.

In [13], an input signal in the form

$$V_{\text{in}}(t) = \sum_{i=0}^M A_i \sin(2\pi f_i t + \theta_i), \quad (29)$$

which consists of $(M + 1)$ frequency components, was used for the calibration. As shown in [13], if $f_i \neq k/2MT_s$ for $k = 0, 1, \dots, M/2$, the mean value of multiplication of the outputs of two adjacent sub-ADCs is related to the amount of timing

Fig. 6. Sampling voltages of a 4-channel TI ADC.

skew. In particular, this mean value indicates the polarity of the timing error ΔT between the two adjacent channels, which is sufficient information to try to iteratively force ΔT to go to zero.

In [14], a pilot tone, $A \cos(2\pi f_p t + \theta)$, was used as a calibration signal, as shown in Fig. 5. The digital output of the sub-ADC is then multiplied by both a digital in-phase and a quadrature (I/Q) sinusoidal signal with the same frequency as the input (f_p). It was shown in [14] that the relative timing mismatch (relative to some specific sub-ADC) of the i -th sub-ADC, ΔT_i , can be computed as

$$\Delta T_i = \frac{\tan^{-1}(Q/I)}{2\pi f_p}. \quad (30)$$

The accuracy of (30) depends on the accuracy of the digital I/Q sinusoidal waveforms. For high-speed ADCs, the I/Q signals are required to have a very low quantization noise, something that might be difficult to achieve.

One major, albeit usually overlooked, problem associated with most of the foreground timing skew calibration methods where a specific input is applied to compute the timing error (specifically the ones where the input signal’s slope is a determining factor e.g. [11]) is the fact that using this technique the offset error of a sub-ADC cannot be distinguished from its timing error. This requires the sub-ADCs to have a very low offset, and demands a dedicated and accurate offset mismatch calibration circuit.

2) *Background*: A number of techniques for background calibration of timing error in interleaved ADCs have been proposed in the literature. One method is based on using *zero crossing* [15], [16]. For an input signal $x(t)$ that is continuous in both time and amplitude, a zero crossing (ZC) occurs when $x(t)$ changes its polarity (at the net of its dc value) from positive to negative, and vice versa. For instance, in Fig. 6, which demonstrates the first sampling instances of a 4-channel TI ADC, there is a zero crossing between $x_2[0]$ and $x_3[0]$, and another between $x_2[1]$ and $x_3[1]$. It was shown in [15] that if $x(t)$ is sinusoidal of frequency f_i and if the ratio f_i/f_s is irrational, the probability of ZC between two adjacent samplers, $x_i[k]$ and $x_i[k+1]$, is proportional to their sampling interval. Thus, the sampling interval can be found by detecting ZC and used to detect mismatches between sampling intervals of all channels with reference to one channel [16]. A drawback of this technique is that the offset of the comparators that are used to detect the zero crossings cannot be distinguished from the timing error, which is tackled in [15] by using high-pass filters preceding the comparators to suppress their offset.

Ref. [5] used a frequency-domain method. This is similar to the gain mismatch calibration method discussed in Section II, since it is also based on the fact that the timing mismatch between channels causes spurs at the same frequencies as the gain mismatch does, but with a 90° phase shift. As such, the circuit implementation is very similar to Fig. 2 with an

Fig. 7. Timing mismatch calibration in the frequency domain.

addition of a 90° phase-shift all-pass filter, as shown in Fig. 7. The realization of the 90° phase-shift is non-trivial. Ref. [5] simply used $H(z) = z^{-1}$, which only has a 90° phase shift at $f = f_s/4$.

One category of the background timing-skew detection techniques is based on finding a *timing function* of the sub-ADC outputs that is proportional to their corresponding timing error. One such timing function is simply a mean-square difference between the outputs of two adjacent sub-ADCs, that is

$$\overline{D_{\Delta T}} = E [(y_{i+1}[k] - y_i[k])^2], \quad (31)$$

where $y_i[k]$ is the k -th output of the i -th channel where $0 < i < M - 1$. It was claimed in [3] that this timing function is proportional to the timing error between the two channels. Intuitively speaking, if the sampling interval between the two adjacent sub-ADCs is shorter than $T_s = 1/f_s$, the ADC input signal will change less between the samples (on average) compared to when this interval is greater than T_s . This claim is only true if the input signal is band-limited to the Nyquist frequency ($f_s/2$). In [17], a similar timing function was proposed, namely

$$\overline{D_{\Delta T}} = E [(y_{i+1}[k] - y_i[k])^2] - E [(y_{i+2}[k] - y_{i+1}[k])^2], \quad (32)$$

and it was shown that

$$\overline{D_{\Delta T}} \approx -4\Delta T \frac{dR_{in}}{d\tau}, \quad (33)$$

where $dR_{in}/d\tau$ is the time derivative of the autocorrelation of the input at the sampling moments. The average of the product of the outputs of two interleaved channels can also be used as a measure of the timing mismatch. Ref. [18] used a similar method. This approach, however, fails for some specific cases, e.g. when the input is a single-tone sinusoidal signal. In order to get around this problem, [1] proposed using two products: the product of an odd sample of channel 1 and the next even sample of channel 2, and the product of an even sample of channel 1 and the next odd sample of channel 2. It was shown in [1] that the average of the difference between the two products is proportional to the timing error ΔT , that is

$$\overline{D_{\Delta T}} = E [y_1[k]y_2[k-1] - y_1[k-1]y_2[k]] \quad (34)$$

$$\approx -2\Delta T \frac{dR_{in}}{d\tau}. \quad (35)$$

These types of timing functions all rely on one channel to be ideal and detect the timing mismatches of other channels with respect to that ideal channel. This would make the realization of timing functions excessively complex as the number of channels increases, since the channels need to be calibrated one by one, marking the previously calibrated channels as the reference one. One solution to this problem is to employ a separate *reference* sub-ADC with respect to which all of the other sub-ADCs would be calibrated. For instance, [19] used a reference ADC which is identical to the sub-ADCs, and its

Fig. 8. Illustration of the autocorrelation as a function of timing mismatch.

sampling time aligns with that of each sub-ADC. With no timing errors, the outputs of the reference ADC and of the corresponding aligned sub-ADC are identical. Otherwise, the difference between the two can be used as a measure of the timing mismatch. In general, if the sampling frequency of the reference ADC is set to f_s/L and

$$\gcd(L, M) = 1, \quad (36)$$

where $\gcd(p, q)$ denotes the greatest common divisor of integers p and q , the sampling instance of the reference ADC coincides with that of a specific sub-ADC once for every $L \cdot M$ samples. One issue associated with this simple timing mismatch calibration method is the limited accuracy of the timing error detection. The minimum detectable timing error is equal to

$$\Delta T_{\min} = \text{LSB}/m, \quad (37)$$

where m is the slope of the input signal. For instance, for our case-study ADC with a full-scale range of 1 V , LSB is roughly $250\ \mu\text{V}$ and m can be as high as $0.5 \times 2\pi f_{in} \approx 10\ \text{V/ns}$ ($f_{in} = 3.2\ \text{GHz}$). This results in $\Delta T_{\min} \approx 24\ \text{fs}$ which is larger than the requirement of (26). Using the same technique, [20] achieved a finer resolution of the timing error detection by dithering the sampling time of the reference ADC in a pseudorandom manner. In [21], the cross-correlation between the outputs of the sub-ADCs and the output of the reference ADC at the coincidence of the sampling times (which is basically the autocorrelation of the output signal of each channel) was proposed as a measure of the timing mismatch. It was proved in [21] that for an interleaved ADC, the maximum output SNR is achieved when the autocorrelation of the output of the individual sub-ADCs is maximized, as graphically illustrated in Fig. 8. Therefore, to minimize the timing error of one sub-ADC, the cross-correlation of the output of that sub-ADC with the output of the reference ADC should be maximized. One advantage of this technique is that, since the cross-correlation between the outputs of sub-ADC and reference ADC does not require the transfer functions of both ADCs to be identical, it is possible to reduce the resolution of the reference ADC to only one bit (i.e. a single comparator). Moreover, the reference ADC can operate at a lower conversion rate, thus at a lower power consumption, compared to the sub-ADCs. It was mentioned in [22] that this timing mismatch calibration technique does not easily lend itself to high-resolution converters if the input source impedance is finite. Another drawback of this cross-correlation-based timing mismatch calibration is that it is heavily reliant on the statistics of the input, and requires the input signal to be wide-band stationary (WBS). This is not necessarily the case for all communication channels.

A category of the timing mismatch calibration techniques that does not depend on the statistics of the input signal uses a *derivative* of the input voltage to correct the timing error. The

Fig. 9. A derivative-based timing mismatch detection scheme along with the LMS implementation.

Fig. 10. Sign determination of the input derivative at the sampling moment.

core idea of all derivative-based calibration algorithms is that, given an input signal $x(t)$, if the sampled values are skewed by ΔT from the ideal sampling timestamps kT ($k = 0, 1, \dots$), the sampled signal values can be modeled by the first-order Taylor expansion approximation as

$$x(kT + \Delta T) \approx x(kT) + \Delta T \left. \frac{dx}{dt} \right|_{t=kT}. \quad (38)$$

The error term thus would be equal to

$$e = D \cdot \Delta T, \quad (39)$$

where D is the derivative of the input signal at the sampling moment. If D is known, the term $e \cdot D$ can be used to force ΔT to zero, e.g. via an LMS algorithm. For this technique to work, the sole knowledge of the sign of D would be sufficient (i.e. a sign-sign LMS algorithm). In order to obtain (the sign of) D , [23] proposed to use an auxiliary ADC with a different input RC time constant, as shown in Fig. 9. As can be seen, the bandwidth of the auxiliary ADC is intentionally lowered by putting a series resistance of value ΔR in the signal path in order to delay the input signal. By working out the transfer function from the input to the difference of the output voltages of the auxiliary and reference ADCs, it can be shown that the output is proportional to the derivative of the input [23].

Ref. [24] proposed a way of determining the derivative of the input without using an auxiliary ADC, by claiming that the slope

$$m_{\text{avg}} = \frac{y[k+1] - y[k-1]}{2T_s} \quad (40)$$

has the same sign as the ideal slope at the sampling instant, as shown in Fig. 10. Again, this is only valid as long as the input is within the Nyquist limit. The block diagram implementation of such a method is shown in Fig. 11. Here, the subtraction of the outputs of sub-ADC $_{i+1}$ and sub-ADC $_{i-1}$ produces an output whose sign is the same as that of the input signal derivative at the sampling instant of sub-ADC $_i$.

In [4], a product of a sub-ADC output with its derivative is used for the timing error detection as follows. Each sub-ADC output \tilde{D}_{out} can be seen as a sum of an ideal signal D_{out} and an error term ΔD_{out} : $\tilde{D}_{\text{out}} = D_{\text{out}} + \Delta D_{\text{out}}$. Therefore, the average product of the sub-ADC output and its derivative at the sampling instant is given by

Fig. 11. Modification of Fig. 9 with the delayed auxiliary ADC replaced by two adjacent sub-ADCs.

$$\tilde{D}_{\text{out}} \cdot \frac{dD_{\text{out}}}{dt} \approx \overline{(D_{\text{out}} + \Delta D_{\text{out}}) \cdot \frac{dD_{\text{out}}}{dt}} \quad (41)$$

$$= D_{\text{out}} \cdot \frac{dD_{\text{out}}}{dt} + \Delta D_{\text{out}} \cdot \frac{dD_{\text{out}}}{dt}. \quad (42)$$

The ideal signal is orthogonal to its derivative, making the first term in (42) zero. Also, according to (39), $\Delta D_{\text{out}} \approx \Delta T \cdot dD_{\text{out}}/dt$. Hence, the timing error can be estimated by

$$\Delta T = \frac{\tilde{D}_{\text{out}} \cdot \frac{dD_{\text{out}}}{dt}}{\left(\frac{dD_{\text{out}}}{dt} \right)^2}. \quad (43)$$

One major issue associated with the class of derivative techniques is that they depend on the statistics of the derivative of the input signal. For instance, low input frequencies for long periods of time carry very little information in the derivative. Furthermore, having the system's noise power greater than the "derivative power" could also be an issue.

B. Correction

1) *Analog*: Analog correction of the timing error is usually performed using a variable-delay line (VDL). A VDL is basically a digital-to-time converter (DTC) that delays the input clock by a certain amount that is controlled by a digital code [25] [26]. To adjust the skewed clocks of the sub-ADCs of a TI ADC, each clock signal is delayed by a VDL placed just before the sampling switch of the corresponding sub-ADC. For a TI ADC, a VDL is usually implemented as an inverter with a digitally controlled capacitor in a binary-weighted structure at its output [16], [21], [23]. To achieve fine delay resolution for the VDL, the capacitors are implemented using MOSFETs. In [1], a degenerated inverter is used where the degeneration resistor can be adjusted by a variable resistor. A constant slope method reported in [25] can provide a fine resolution of 100 fs with a 9-bit range.

One of the main drawbacks of the analog correction is the jitter introduced by the VDL, which might become problematic when a high timing resolution is required.

2) *Digital*: Correction in the digital domain can be performed by means of a finite impulse-response (FIR) filter as follows. Let us assume that a sub-ADC is sampled with a sampling timing error of τ seconds. The output $y[n]$ can be represented, in the z -domain as

$$Z \{x[n - \tau/T]\} = z^{-\tau/T} X(z), \quad (44)$$

and in the Fourier domain as

$$\mathcal{F} \{x[n - \tau/T]\} = e^{-j\omega\tau/T} X(e^{j\omega}). \quad (45)$$

where T is the sampling interval. In (45), the term $e^{-j\omega\tau/T}$ (denoted by H_d) is a 'filter' which represents the delay of

the input signal. The impulse response of this filter is readily given by

$$h_d[n] = \frac{\sin[\pi \cdot (n - \tau/T)]}{\pi \cdot (n - \tau/T)} = \text{sinc}(n - \tau/T). \quad (46)$$

When τ/T is an integer, the impulse response of (46) reduces to a single impulse at $n = \tau$. For noninteger values of τ , however, the impulse response is an infinitely long, shifted and sampled version of the sinc function and usually referred to as *fractional delay filter*. For a practical implementation, this impulse response needs to be approximated by a causal response of finite order. The order of the approximate filter determines the accuracy towards which the timing correction can be performed. The approximation can be done through the least-square-mean (LMS) method or by using Lagrange interpolation [27]. For an M -channel TI ADC, where there are M different delay filters, the correction of the input signal becomes a reconstruction problem of M -order filter bank [28]–[30]. It is well known that if the average sampling period is shorter than the signal Nyquist rate, a ‘perfect’ reconstruction to within the limits of the quantizers is possible.

The digital-domain correction takes advantage of the technology scaling but the complex digital reconstruction filter for error acquisition limits the signal bandwidth.

V. PROPOSED CALIBRATION TECHNIQUE

We propose a calibration technique that is not only able to effectively calibrate the timing mismatches between different channels of an interleaved ADC but also, and at the same time, to correct for their offset mismatches. The proposed calibration method is foreground and detects the mismatches in the digital domain.

Fig. 12 shows a block diagram of the proposed calibration method for an N -bit M -channel TI ADC. It is composed of the calibration unit, M k -bit digital-to-time converters (DTC) and a dedicated signal generator which is used only during the calibration. During the calibration, the input signal buffer (Buffer₁) is disabled (EN_{calib} high is asserted), exhibiting high-impedance at its output, and the calibration buffer (Buffer₂, which can be identical to Buffer₁) is switched on. This configuration prevents using series switches, which would impair the maximum achievable bandwidth of the ADC. The function of the DTCs is to delay the input mismatched clock of each channel by an amount proportional to its k -bit digital input coming from the calibration circuit. Assuming that the DTC is linear and with a resolution of ΔT_d , the maximum covered time range (i.e. the DTC full-scale) is

$$\Delta T_{\text{DTC,FS}} = 2^k \Delta T_d. \quad (47)$$

The idea is to have a periodic input signal $V_{\text{calib}}(t)$ whose frequency f_{calib} is chosen such that, in the absence of timing mismatch (i.e. the sampling clocks CLK₁ to CLK_M are progressively phase-shifted by precisely $2\pi/M$ rad), the voltage sampled by *all of the channels* would be the same (denoted with V_0 from now onward). In the presence of timing mismatch, on the contrary, the voltage samples would differ from V_0 . By denoting with B_0 the binary representation of V_0 (i.e. the ADCs output code for $V_{\text{calib}} = V_0$), the calibration unit then checks the N -bit outputs of the ADCs sequentially, and if a given output is not equal to B_0 , it adjusts the next sampling instance through the k -bit DTC until the output becomes B_0 . The accuracy of such a calibration protocol obviously depends on the resolution of the DTCs (ΔT_d).

Fig. 12. Block diagram of an M -channel TI ADC along with the extra circuitry for the proposed timing-skew calibration.

Fig. 13. Timing diagram for a 4-channel TI ADC with a triangle signal of period $3T_s$ as the input.

An example of a signal which can be employed for such a purpose is a triangle waveform with a period $T_{\text{calib}} = 1/f_s$. The sampling moments coincide with the zero-crossings of the triangle signal ($V_0 = 0$) in an orderly manner. For the ADC to be able to process such a high-frequency input signal, its bandwidth needs to be at least equal to f_s , which may not represent a practical solution. Therefore, a signal with a lower frequency would be preferred. It can be proven that if $T_{\text{calib}} = lT_s$, where l is an arbitrary integer and

$$\text{gcd}(l, M) = 1, \quad (48)$$

then the triangle signal would still have the desired property. The most straightforward choice is $l = M - 1$, for which the sampling instant of each channel coincides with the zero-crossing once in every M samples in a periodic pattern. Fig. 13 illustrates this for the specific case of $M = 4$. The calibration unit then needs to only look at every M -th ADC output of a specific channel to check whether it is equal to B_0 ; if not, it will adjust the sampling clock through the corresponding DTC until the ADC output converges to B_0 . In practice, however, this turns out to be a bit more complicated. This is because the ADC would show an output of B_0 for an input range of $\Delta V = 1 \text{ LSB}$. This is equivalent to a timing difference (error) of $\Delta T = \Delta V/m$, where m is the slope of the input calibration signal, which turns out to be much larger than the requirement imposed by (26). To understand this, let us assume the triangle input calibration signal has a peak-to-peak voltage amplitude of $V_{\text{calib,pp}}$ and period $T_{\text{calib}} = (M - 1)/f_s$ [as per (48)], thus a slope of

$$m = \frac{V_{\text{calib,pp}}}{T_{\text{calib}}/2} = \frac{2f_s V_{\text{calib,pp}}}{M - 1} \quad (49)$$

The output of an N -bit ADC with a full-scale of V_{FS} (hence, the LSB amplitude $V_{\text{LSB}} = V_{\text{FS}}/2^N$) whose input is such a triangle signal would not change for a time duration of

$$\Delta T_{\text{LSB}} = V_{\text{LSB}}/m = \frac{V_{\text{FS}}}{V_{\text{calib,pp}}} \cdot \frac{(M - 1)}{2^{N+1} f_s} \quad (50)$$

For our case-study ADC ($N = 12$, $M = 16$, $f_s = 6.4 \text{ GHz}$, $V_{\text{FS}} = 1 \text{ V}$) and for $V_{\text{calib,pp}} = 0.5 \text{ V}$, ΔT_{LSB} would be

Fig. 14. Timing-skew calibration: (a) without offset, (b) with offset, where ΔT and ΔV_{os} are the timing and offset error, respectively.

equal to 572 fs, which is far larger than the requirement set by (26). In other words, this means that, in the worst case, any timing mismatch below this value would not be detected (thus corrected) by the calibration algorithm. This issue can be readily solved as follows. Let us assume that $\pm\Delta T_{max}$ is the maximum timing-skew that can happen due to both systematic and non-systematic timing mismatches. According to (49), this is equivalent to

$$\Delta V_{max} = m \cdot \Delta T_{max} = \frac{\Delta T_{max}}{T_{calib}/2} V_{calib,pp}. \quad (51)$$

This maximum timing mismatch should be known beforehand as it determines the full-scale range of the DTC's ($\Delta T_{DTC,FS}$) which are employed during the calibration to properly skew the clock. Let us also denote with ΔD_{max} the quantized ADC output which corresponds to ΔV_{max} , i.e.

$$\Delta D_{max} = Q(\Delta V_{max}/V_{LSB}). \quad (52)$$

Clearly, if $\Delta T_{max} < \Delta T_{LSB}$, $\Delta D_{max} = 0$. Now, what the calibration unit must do to calibrate the timing mismatch of the i -th channel of the TI ADC is to progressively increase the delay of CLK_i by means of DTC_i so that the output of ADC_i changes by $\Delta D_{max} + 1$ compared to its initial value. If this is performed for all of the sub-ADCs, the sampling clocks would become almost equally phase shifted (i.e. each ideally with a phase of exactly $2\pi k/M$, with k being the sub-ADC index, $0 < k < M - 1$), with a maximum timing error of ΔT_d (the resolution of the DTC). Fig. 14(a) illustrates this for the case of $\Delta D_{max} = 2$. As can be seen, the sampling signal is ΔT seconds skewed from its ideal point which results in an ADC output of -1 before calibration. The calibration algorithm progressively delays the sampling clock until the ADC output becomes $\Delta D_{max} + 1 = +3$. The amount of the time shift incurred by the clock in this example is $22\Delta T_d$.

Thus far, it has been assumed that the offset of all of the channels was zero. The offset of a channel is also translated into timing mismatch through the voltage-to-time conversion via the ramp slope, that is

$$\Delta T_{os} = \Delta V_{os}/m, \quad (53)$$

where ΔV_{os} and ΔT_{os} are the offset voltage and the offset-induced timing mismatch³. However, this equivalent timing error caused by the offset cannot be ultimately distinguished from the actual timing mismatch by the proposed calibration method. This is illustrated in Fig. 14(b), which shows the case where an offset mismatch of ΔV_{os} is present. As can be seen, this is exactly equivalent to the case of Fig. 14(a) even though no timing mismatch exists.

In order to solve this issue, a triangle signal with frequency of $f_{in} = f_s/(M+1)$ is employed. Such frequency still satisfies

³Note that ΔT_{os} is not the timing mismatch of the actual clock, but the equivalent timing mismatch which would cause the output of an offset-free ADC to be ΔV_{os} .

Fig. 15. Timing diagram for a 3-channel TI ADC with a triangle signal of period $4T_s$ as the input.

the above-mentioned requirements, thus ensuring the proper operation of the proposed calibration method. However, the TI-ADC channels now sample the zero-crossing points on both the rising and falling edges of the triangle signal, as shown in Fig. 15 for the specific case of $M = 3$. The key point here is that a timing mismatch would cause an error $\delta V_{e,r}$ in the sampled voltage on the rising edge which has *opposite* sign compared to the error $\delta V_{e,f}$ in the sampled voltage on the falling edge, i.e. $\delta V_{e,r} > 0$ and $\delta V_{e,f} < 0$ in the case the real clock timestamp is lagging the ideal one. On the contrary, the offset error would cause a sampling voltage error with the *same* sign on both edges (i.e. both $\delta V_{e,r}$ and $\delta V_{e,f} > 0$ in the presence of $\Delta V_{os} > 0$), thus making it possible for the calibration algorithm to distinguish between them. In other terms, the difference x_{calib} between the ADC output associated with a sample on the rising edge of the ramp (henceforth called D_r) and a sample on the falling edge of the ramp (D_f) is free from the ADC offset and retains only the timing error information. This variable is used as an input of the calibration unit.

Fig. 16 illustrates this new sampling scenario in the absence of offset mismatch, and for a timing mismatch $\Delta T = n_d \Delta T_d$, with n_d being an integer (in the example, the real clock timestamp occurs n_d times the DTC resolution step earlier than the nominal one). Under the assumption that the rising slope is exactly the opposite of the falling slope, $D_r = -D_f$ (with respect to the mid-code). The calibration would then delay the clock with steps of ΔT_d by progressively incrementing the DTC input code by 1, while reading out $x_{calib} = D_r - D_f = 2D_r$. Whenever the clock experiences enough delay such that the sampled ADC input crosses a quantization level ($D_r + 1$ in the case of rising slope of the triangle waveform and $D_f - 1$ for the falling slope), x_{calib} increments by 2 (or decrements by 2 in the case the real clock lags the ideal one). As before, the calibration stops when $D_r = \Delta D_{max} + 1$ or, equivalently, when

$$x_{calib} = 2\Delta D_{max} + 2. \quad (54)$$

Assuming that $\Delta T_{LSB} = n_{LSB} \Delta T_d$ is the minimum time shift of the clock such that the ADC output changes by 1 (n_{LSB} is an integer), the initial value of D_r would be

$$D_{r0} = \lfloor \frac{-n_d}{n_{LSB}} \rfloor, \quad (55)$$

where $\lfloor y \rfloor$ is the floor function of the real number y . As the calibration proceeds in the manner described above, a sequence of linearly progressive numbers would then appear at the ADC output, as shown in Fig. 16(b). Here, n_0 is given by

$$n_0 \equiv n_d \pmod{n_{LSB}}, \quad (56)$$

meaning n_d is the modulo of n_0 divided by n_{LSB} .

Fig. 16. (a) Position of the clock signal on the triangle waveform for a timing error of ΔT and zero offset error. (b) the sequence of numbers appearing at the ADC output during the calibration

On the other hand, in face of an input-referred offset of ΔV , as shown in Fig. 17(a), a different pattern of numbers appears at D_r and D_f . This is illustrated in Fig. 17(b), where

$$n_{os} = \lfloor \frac{m\Delta V}{\Delta T_d} \rfloor. \quad (57)$$

As can be observed, an asymmetry is formed in the sequences of D_r and D_f (i.e. D_r is not $-D_f$ anymore) by an amount of n_{os} , which then results in a sequence of $2\Delta D_{max}$ with length $2n_{os}$ at x_{calib} . Therefore, the calibration unit should keep track of the last sequence of numbers before it terminates the calibration and register its length as $2n_{os}$, and the total length of the last two sequences of numbers as n_{LSB} , as depicted in Fig. 17(b). The calibration process ends when x_{calib} becomes equal to $2\Delta D_{max} + 1$. The calibration unit also keeps track of the number of DTC steps from the beginning until the end, which represents the total length of the entire sequence x_{calib} , hereinafter referred to as n_{dt} . The timing and offset mismatch can then be computed as:

$$\Delta T = \Delta D_{max} \cdot n_{LSB} - (n_{dt} - n_{os}) \quad (58)$$

$$\Delta V = \pm n_{os} / n_{LSB}. \quad (59)$$

The sign of ΔV depends on which variable, whether D_r or D_f , becomes ΔD_{max} first, which is also recorded.

In practice, the ideal clock may not be exactly aligned with the zero-crossings of the input triangle waveform upon the start of calibration. This, however, only represents a constant offset common to all of the TI-ADC channels and would therefore not affect the validity of equations (58) and (59).

The proposed calibration technique is similar to the ones reported in [6], [11], [12], where a sinusoidal/triangular signal was used to detect the extent of timing skews. However, our method addresses and solves some of the main drawbacks associated with those and offers the following advantages:

1. As already pointed out in Section IV-A, when the slope of an input signal is used for the extraction of timing mismatches, the offset error also manifests itself with the same effect as

Fig. 17. (a) Position of the clock signal on the triangle waveform for a timing error of ΔT and an offset error of ΔV . (b) the sequence of numbers appearing at the ADC output during the calibration

the timing error, and thus is indistinguishable with it. This basically means that the offset mismatch of different channels should be corrected with the same required precision as the timing mismatch (when converted to voltage by the slope of the input signal). For the method discussed in [6], for instance, where the sampling clock (with a frequency of $f_s = 6.4$ GHz and an amplitude of $1 V_{pp}$) is used as the input signal during the calibration, the slope of the input can be as high as $m = 0.5V \times 2\pi f_s \approx 20$ V/ns, and therefore, to satisfy (26), the resolution of the offset calibration should be at least $m \times LSB \approx 200 \mu V$. Although this is achievable for this specific case, the required precision is frequency-dependent and might become very difficult or even impossible to achieve at higher sampling frequencies. For example, in the case of $f_s = 30$ GHz, the resolution of the offset mismatch calibration should be around $40 \mu V$. As discussed in detail earlier in Section V, the proposed method does not suffer from this drawback.

2. The timing-skew calibration scheme proposed here *concurrently* corrects for the offset mismatch, without the need for dedicated extra circuitry.

3. For a Nyquist-rate ADC, the maximum required input bandwidth should be $f_s/2$. Refs. [6], [11], [12] all used the actual sampling clock with a frequency of f_s as the input signal for the calibration process. This poses the unnecessary requirement on the ADC bandwidth to be $2\times$ higher than what is actually needed for the normal conversion, and thus ultimately entails higher design complexity and power consumption. The input signal for our proposed calibration method is $M/2$ times slower than the Nyquist frequency, with M being the number of interleaved channels.

VI. NONIDEALITIES

A. Triangle Signal Non-Linearity

The triangle signal can be generated by an integrator with a square wave input signal of frequency $f_{\text{calib}} = f_s/(M+1)$. Thus far, it has been assumed that the positive slope of the triangle signal is equal to the negative slope. It has been also assumed that the positive and negative edges are straight lines. Yet, this requirement should only be fulfilled for a voltage range of $\Delta V_{\text{max}} = m \cdot \Delta T_{\text{max}}$. Since ΔT_{max} , which is the maximum timing skew of the ADC, is usually in the order of tens of ps, ΔV_{max} is only few millivolts. It is then reasonable to assume that the triangle waveform is linear within this small voltage range. Moreover, given that the triangle waveform generated by the integrator is more linear around its mid-range (i.e. zero-crossings), it is convenient, before the calibration is asserted, to internally time-shift the waveform using coarse time steps, thus allowing the sampling clock timestamps to occur within such linear voltage region, e.g. using a coarse DTC like the one used in [26].

A low-cost way of generating a triangle signal is as follows: the ADC sampling clock is fed into a divide-by-16 circuit, which is made of four back-to-back D flip-flops. The output square wave signal is then input to a multi-order passive RC low-pass filter producing the desired triangular signal of smaller amplitude. As discussed above, the requirements on this signal are: 1) the linearity around the mid-point for a small range of a few LSBs must be lower than ΔT set by (26), and 2) the slopes of the rising and falling edges of the calibration signal in this range are equal so that the maximum voltage difference (error) between those edges in this desired range is lower than $\Delta V = m \cdot \Delta T$, where ΔT and m are given by (26) and (49), respectively. For our case-study ADC with $f_s = 6.4$ GHz, a 3rd-order RC filter with $R = 1$ k Ω and $C = 200$ fF and an input of 1 V_{pp} results in a triangle output of 480 mV_{pp} at $f_s/16 = 400$ MHz, where the rising and falling edges differ by a maximum amount of < 3 μ V for a range of 8 LSBs around the middle point. This difference is equivalent to $3 \mu\text{V}/m = 9.9$ fs in time (see Eq. (50)), which is less than the minimum requirement of (26).

B. Capacitive DAC and DTC Non-Linearity

So far, we have assumed that the capacitive DAC (CAP-DAC) of each SAR-ADC channel is perfectly linear (i.e. zero DNL and INL). Unfortunately, and unlike with the offset mismatch, the non-linearity of the CAP-DAC, which directly impacts on the whole ADC non-linearity, cannot be distinguished from the timing mismatch errors. Quantitatively, a DAC INL error of ΔV_{INL} is equivalent to a timing mismatch of

$$\Delta T = \Delta V_{\text{INL}}/m, \quad (60)$$

or equivalently

$$\sigma_{\Delta T} = \sigma_{\text{INL}}/m, \quad (61)$$

which however cannot be calibrated by the proposed timing skew calibration algorithm, as explained in the following. Per our earlier discussion, the sampling clock timestamps occur around the zero-crossings of the input signal (either a triangle wave or a sine wave) during the calibration. This corresponds to the ADC's mid-scale, which is also the level at which the CAP-DAC exhibits greater nonlinearity (i.e. maximum INL). The standard deviation of this maximum INL is given by

$$\sigma_{\text{INL}} = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_0 \sqrt{2^N - 1} V_{\text{LSB}}, \quad (62)$$

where σ_0 is the relative standard deviation of an LSB capacitor of the CAP-DAC [i.e. $\sigma_{(\Delta C_u/C_u)}$]. By substituting (62) into (61), we have

$$\sigma_{\Delta T} = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_0 \sqrt{2^N - 1} V_{\text{LSB}}/m = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_0 \sqrt{2^N - 1} \Delta T_{\text{LSB}}. \quad (63)$$

In advanced technologies, σ_0 is well below 1% for a 1 fF MOM capacitor. Let us now assume that, for the case-study ADC, the binary DAC has a unity capacitor of 1 fF; this would result in an equivalent timing mismatch [due to the INL error derived in (63)] of about 210 fs, which largely violates (26).

The proposed solution to overcome such an issue relies on the fact that only a small portion of the whole ADC full-scale range (and hence of the full-scale of the DAC) is exercised during the calibration. Indeed, assuming that

$$\Delta T_{\text{max}} = \alpha \Delta T_{\text{LSB}}, \quad (64)$$

an ADC with a resolution of $\log_2(\alpha+1)$ -bit would be enough to cover the maximum timing error for the calibration. ΔT_{max} is in order of a few picoseconds, which makes α less than 4 for our case-study ADC, where $\Delta T_{\text{LSB}} = 650$ fs. Therefore, a 3-bit ADC would be sufficient for the timing-skew calibration to be functional. The advantage here is that the equivalent timing error induced by the ADC INL error [as per (63)] would now be significantly lower. For the case of $N = 3$, the equivalent timing mismatch would only be equal to 8.5 fs, which satisfies the minimum timing requirement of (26). From a practical perspective, it is straightforward to convert a 10-bit SAR ADC to a 3-bit one, which is achieved by involving in the conversion only the 3 LSB bits of the DAC, while freezing the rest of the bits⁴. That is, after the sampling phase, the SAR conversion only acts on the last 3 LSB capacitors (i.e. those associated with bits B_2 , B_1 and B_0).

The DTC nonlinearity manifests itself in the form of an accumulated output error when its input is swept by the calibration unit. If the DTC has a maximum peak-to-peak INL of $\text{INL}_{\text{DTC,max}}$, the maximum output error of the DTC cannot be larger than $\text{INL}_{\text{DTC,max}}$. This essentially means that the timing mismatch is going to be calibrated by a timing resolution of $\Delta T_d + \text{INL}_{\text{DTC,max}}$ rather than ΔT_d .

The noise of the ADC plus the noise of the waveform generator can be easily canceled out by averaging. This means the input waveform can be read out by the ADC multiple times and then averaged out.

C. Gain Mismatch

Basically, what the gain error does is that it changes the slope of the input-output characterization of the sub-ADC, therein shrinking/expanding the LSB by the amount of the gain error, which we assume is $\alpha\%$. The time equivalent to this voltage error (transformed by the slope of the triangle waveform) is $\alpha \times \Delta T_{\text{LSB}}$, where $\Delta T_{\text{LSB}} = V_{\text{LSB}}/m$ (see Eq. (50)) and is equal to 572 fs for our case-study ADC. This gain-induced error should be less than the requirement of (26), i.e. 11.5 fs. This results in $\alpha < 2\%$, which is by the way a very easy target to achieve for a 12-bit ADC for instance (for a 12-bit resolution, 2% is about 82 LSBs.).

⁴The same can be done for a pipelined SAR ADC by freezing the first stages and the first few bits of the last stage. For instance, for a two-stage 10-bit ADC, with the first 6 bits being resolved in the first stage, the complete first stage and the first MSB bit of the second stage need to be frozen.

Fig. 18. Output spectrum before (a) and after calibration (b).

VII. SIMULATION RESULTS

The proposed calibration technique has been verified through simulations by using algorithmic models for both the calibration unit and the constituent blocks of the core ADC. The outlined modeling case scenario is a 6.4 GS/s 12-bit 15-channel time-interleaved ADC. The sub-ADCs are modeled as conventional SAR ADC converters with binary-weighted capacitive DAC. A random mismatch normal distribution is added to the DAC capacitors, assuming a standard deviation of the unit capacitance (i.e. the LSB capacitor) equal to 1% of its nominal value C_u . The standard deviation of the other capacitors (i.e. from the LSB + 1 up to the MSB) increases proportionally to the square root of their value, i.e. $\sigma_C = 1\% \cdot \sqrt{C \cdot C_u}$.

Timing and offset mismatches are modeled as normally-distributed random variables with standard deviation of 0.2 ps and 2 LSB, respectively. A noise of 1 mV_{RMS} is also added to the input so as to account for the input-referred noise of the ADC, the kT/C noise and the noise of the input signal. The input signal used for calibration is a triangle signal with a frequency of $f_{\text{calib}} = f_s/16$. The resolution of the DTC, which is basically the resolution of the DTC, is set to 10 fs (this can be achieved by the DTC proposed in [6] or [31]). Random mismatch is also added to the DTC, in such a way that the maximum peak-to-peak INL is about 1LSB (i.e. 10 fs). A $\eta_{\text{avg}}=1024\times$ averaging is performed to diminish the effect of random noise. Finally, a 100-run Monte-Carlo simulation is executed based on the aforementioned characteristics and we report worst-case results in terms of the output SNDR. The results are depicted in Fig. 18 for an input frequency of $f_{\text{in}}=3.12$ GHz. As can be seen, the SFDR improves by 35 dB, thus proving the effectiveness of the proposed calibration technique. It is straightforward to demonstrate that the total calibration takes about $n_{\text{LSB}} \cdot (\Delta D_{\text{max}} + 1) \cdot M \cdot n_{\text{avg}} \cdot T_s$ seconds, where $n_{\text{LSB}} = \Delta T_{\text{LSB}}/\Delta T_d$ and ΔT_{LSB} , ΔD_{max} and ΔT_d are given by (50), (52) and (47), respectively. For the analyzed test-case, this time duration is around 600 μs . The foreground calibration routine should run cyclically and only works for applications where a loss of data is available and/or can be tolerated. For example, for a transceiver that sends and receives signals on the same I/O pin at different times, the transmit phase can be used for the calibration.

CONCLUSION

Although interleaving increases the maximum achievable sampling rate of an ADC and may also improve its overall power efficiency in case of pushing the technology limits, the performance degradation caused by mismatches between the channels introduces design challenges which need to be carefully addressed. There exist numerous calibration techniques proposed in the literature. There is a number of factors that should be taken into account when evaluating the effectiveness of an interchannel mismatch calibration technique,

which include the power and area overhead, the precision of the calibration, its conversion time, etc. Furthermore, it should also be assessed how different sources of interchannel mismatch (i.e. offset, gain and timing) mutually interfere while impacting the ADC performance. In this article, a new timing-skew calibration technique was proposed, which concurrently allows detecting the amount of offset mismatch between the channels. The simulation results prove the effectiveness of such technique by showing an improvement of 35 dB in the ADC SFDR after the calibration.

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